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Man-Woman Relationships in Gloria Naylor's *The Men of Brewster Place*

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Abstract:

Due to the legacy of slavery, the structure of black families has been disturbed to such an extent that black people find it rather challenging to maintain a lasting and loving relationship among the family members, especially between husband and wife. Many black women are forced to bear the dual responsibility of both parents for their children and sometimes even for their grandchildren. The employment vulnerability and the limited opportunities available to black people even after so many years of emancipation profoundly affect African-American family life. The frustration they face due to the deferral of their dreams and ambitions in a white racist society results in an unending discord and violence in domestic life. Though some couple are wise enough to cope up with the adverse circumstances, there are many who become victim of their own expectations to fit into the accepted moulds of man and woman in the dominant culture. This paper focuses on the dynamics of man-woman relationships in the black community in Gloria Naylor's *The Men of Brewster Place*.

Keywords: Vulnerability, Emancipation, Deferral, Imperialism, Scrutiny, Dynamics.

Introduction

The Men of Brewster Place (1998) as a sequel to Naylor's debut novel *The Women of Brewster Place* (1982) comprises a collection of linked portraits of the inhabitants of the urban housing project. Primarily, the novel narrates the stories of misfortunes and frustrations of the male residents who once caused havoc in the lives of the women. Though the novel predominantly narrates black men's blues, it also gives a close scrutiny to the lives of women from male perspective. Naylor presents a different version of the same story as "there are just too many sides to the whole story" (Naylor, *Mama Day* 311). Having told the women's side of the story in her debut novel, *The Women of Brewster Place*, Naylor returns to the familiar setting of Brewster Place to focus on men. As Ben, a reliable narrator with the objective tone asserts: "I don't know a man who would be anywhere without a woman. And don't know a woman who'd be anywhere without a man" (*The Men of Brewster Place* 7). Ben presents the view that both man and woman are complementary to each other, rejecting the view that both are distinct entities or binary opposites.

In this novel Naylor focuses her attention on "those intimate relationships in which the most painful consequences of racism are played out" including love relationships, family bonds and friendships (Wall 6). The author highlights the strong presence of a variety of women in the lives of these men who force or guide or lead them to do better in a society that is deeply influenced by the notions of patriarchy, European imperialism and racial superiority or inferiority. Exhorted by their grandmothers, mothers and wives, these men dare to change their lives " 'cause it takes courage to live with change. But if there was a woman anywhere around him, he had to hope for better 'cause she was the other half; the other arm, the other eye—stepping right up on his shoulders to reach for a dream" (8). Going by the rule of Nature, they

keep faith in change, instead of following the static social stereotypes in man-woman relationships.

Ben-Elvira relationship is full of contradictory emotions as Ben recalls his wife Elvira as a self-respecting and educated black woman who is so much proud of herself that nobody can take her for granted. It is due to her heightened self-esteem that men find it difficult to beguile her and call her “Evil Elvira ...cause she was known not to be easy” (*The Men of Brewster Place* 20). She has a good taste for reading and writing which is reflected in the way she reads a magazine or book as and when she gets relieved of her cleaning job. It is her obsession with reading books that provides her knowledge enough to face the challenges of life in the world of racism and sexism. It is because of her strong sense of self and progressive nature that Elvira is able to live a dignified life despite all the horrible circumstances for a black woman in white America.

Ben, a shoeshine boy, is stunned to see such a forceful black woman as he admits that “coming from my time and my place, it was a big thing to catch a good woman who could do both. I imagined her standing up there at City Hall and writing her name large with a flourish at the end. Perfect penmanship” (20). Elvira, a self-respecting woman, never goes for compromises with the priorities and preferences of her life. When Ben proposes her for marriage, she accepts the proposal with a condition that they will have to leave Memphis as its environment doesn't suit her. Elvira is an ambitious black woman who desires to improve the miserable living standard of her family at any cost. She is very tough towards both her husband and daughter as she feels that they are work shirkers. Elvira is pained at heart as she is denied of her heartfelt desire of having more children who would have helped her in the field. Her rough and cruel treatment towards their sweet but disabled daughter emerges out of her frustration of having no

more children. When Ben tries to defend their daughter saying that she tries her best to help them no matter how long it takes her to complete any task; Elvira admonishes him, saying: “She ain’t doing the best she can, and I’m sick of carrying the load for a half-grown woman and a no-count man. Both of you lazy as sin” (*The Men of Brewster Place* 21-22).

To Elvira, complete motherhood does mean bearing healthy children. Motherhood not only helps black women sustain human life but also empowers them to overcome the oddities of domestic life. A close estimation of Elvira’s character reveals that she is not indifferent to the plight of her invalid daughter, but she is against her vulnerability as a black girl. The attitude she adopts towards the girl is only to make her tough enough to face the challenges in the racist and sexist world. Frustrated with the perpetual poverty and struggle for survival, Elvira develops bitterness towards her husband, Ben, who fails to bring any happiness to her life. She doesn’t want to make her life more miserable by inviting the wrath of their white master, who has rented them some extra land in lieu of their services to him. Though Ben is torn apart by the insensitivity Elvira shows towards their only daughter and desires to kill her either by smashing her head between his calloused hands or by ripping her breast with his shotgun, he feels himself totally powerless against the forceful behaviour of his wife as she articulates the hard and bitter truth of their life:

If you was half a man, you coulda given me more babies and we woulda had some help workin’ this land instead of a half-grown woman we gotta carry the load for. And if you was even a quarter of a man, we wouldn’t be a bunch of miserable sharecroppers on someone else’s land—but we is, Ben. And I’ll be damned if I’ll see the little bit we got taken away ’cause you believe that gal’s low-down lies. (26)

Elvira's fearless and assertive personality does not allow Ben to inflict any kind of physical violence on her which he keeps buried in his heart. When their daughter leaves home secretly and goes to Memphis, Ben feels completely crushed within. The aversion he has for Elvira makes their life worst ever. As Elvira finds no hope in their marital relationship, she prefers to step out of the suffocating bond and begins a new life with another man who works on the next plantation. Contrary to the accepted standards of social behaviour that force woman to suffer silently in a hopeless marriage, Elvira moves forward in life and asserts her female identity by choosing her own way of living. Through the character of Elvira, the novelist highlights the modern black woman who refuses to stay in an incompatible marriage to assert her individuality. The author also suggests that the failure of marriages in black community has nothing to do with the assertive self of black woman, rather it is the financial crisis faced by black men that strains most of the relationships.

Mildred is a single parent of her only child, Jerome, who is a mentally retarded boy having the mind of a three-year-old even at the age of seventeen. As a strong woman, she faces the difficulties and challenges of life courageously. She has the knack to take bold decisions as she refuses "to marry the boy's daddy" for one reason or the other (Naylor, *The Men of Brewster Place* 33). Despite her belief that she has been punished by God either for disrespecting the Church or rejecting the marriage proposal, Mildred doesn't waste away her life weeping and cursing; rather she enjoys her life with full vitality. She earns her livelihood by working as a dry cleaner from Monday to Friday and arranges parties at home on the weekend to fill the void of her life with laughter and fun.

By portraying Mildred in such contrasting colours, Naylor highlights the predicament of a single black working mother who finds it quite burdensome to take care of her special child

while working outside home at the same time. The stress of being the only breadwinner in the family can clearly be seen in her fluctuating behaviour toward her son. Mildred, who earlier thought of Jerome as a punishment from God for her own actions, now considers him as a precious gift from God. Whenever she has to go to work, she makes Jerome sit at the piano near the windows. The sunlight coming through the windows brings the blues that keep him unmoved. Though still at the age of seven he is not able even to discharge wastes from body, he can play the piano for the whole day as long as there is light from the windows. Through his music, he tells the sorrows of black people who are made to suffer too much in the racist, classist, and sexist white society. Sometimes his piano seems to read his own life as he plays:

Hot time mama

Hot as she can be

...

Stepped into the ocean

And boiled away the sea

Lord, that woman's sweet

But she's too hot for me. (The Men of Brewster Place 32-33)

This song, coming directly from the heart of Jerome underscores the complex character of his mother Mildred, who is as tough as mild is. Naylor highlights the testing circumstances that make it compulsory for a single black mother to be hard-hearted and assertive in behaviour. It is her resilience and carefree style of living that gives her the courage to face the challenging situations of life in the hegemonic white society.

Basil-Helen relationship also fails because of the burden black men feel to fit themselves into the mould of ideal man as designed by the hegemonic power structure. Basil works hard for

three years undertaking two full-time jobs and a part-time on Sunday to return her mother the hard-earned money she has spent on him for the bail that he jumped over. He is so guilty of his selfish behaviour that he decides to be a solid family man who takes proper care of his wife and children. In the search for a good wife, he comes to a new understanding of the complex behaviour of women as he realizes that “this is where I’ll never understand women in a hundred million years” (50). Earlier, he was obviously afraid of women who exacted commitment from him, but now women suspect his intentions when he asks them for commitment too early, just after their first meeting:

A lot of games were out there; you’d go dizzy trying to figure it out. Sure, may be women had a lot of bad experience with men to make them that cautious. But I saw that black men weren’t the only reason for the mess black women were in. Women yell about finding a man to settle down with; but when one comes along they put him through a lot of crap before they believe. (51)

Basil likes Helen, who is a highly educated woman with a solid family background. Even though she is from a wealthy family as her parents are established in a lucrative profession of dentistry, she does not rely on them for financial support, rather works as a secretary in an office while pursuing a master degree. Though she is not what we call a pretty woman as far as the prevailing parameters of beauty are concerned, she is very attractive with nut-brown skin, short natural hair, and a well-built physique. Besides having a good sense of humour, she is an intelligent and practical woman who doesn’t allow anybody to enter her private life. It is only after the period of three months of dating with Basil and after getting approval from her girlfriend; Helen finds Basil good enough to be introduced to her parents. Basil underscores the power of sisterhood which plays a significant role in determining the life of a woman, saying:

“Never underestimate the power of those girlfriends. They can help to tear you down or build you up with just two phone calls” (*The Men of Brewster Place* 52).

Helen, a self-respecting woman, determines to make a life for herself on her own terms. When Basil showers much affection on the children of her spoiled cousin Keisha, she tries hard to get him away from them thinking that it will bring about only tension in their relationships, saying: “I see where you’re heading, Basil, and there’s nothing waiting for you but trouble. Maybe you aren’t interested in Keisha but the closer you get to those children, the more difficult it’s going to be to leave” (56). Helen is wise enough to foresee the kind of mess it would be if she marries Basil, who is obsessed with the thought of improving the miserable life of little kids of Keisha.

When Basil proposes her for marriage with a compelling urge to adopt Keisha’s children, Helen doesn’t take a second thought in deciding what is good for her. She vehemently rejects his offer, saying: “Basil, if I marry you—or any man—I’ll want to have my own children” (57). Realising that Basil’s ever-growing concern for Keisha’s children would make it difficult for her to live a peaceful life with him, she decides to break up with him. By exhibiting the assertive behaviour of Helen, Naylor underscores the growing independence of an educated black woman who doesn’t find it compulsory for her to marry a man only for the sake of marriage; rather she considers every aspect of life before entering into a marital alliance to ensure its sustainability.

While Helen is quite a nice girl with good sense of humour; her cousin, Keisha, is a woman far from being called good woman in the traditional sense due to her fussy and irritable behaviour. Keisha is barely twenty and mothers two sons: Jason and Eddie. She treats her little sons badly and often beats them for their negligence while doing some tasks. Her chance meeting with Basil at Sinai Baptist brings about a tremendous change in her sons’ life. Partly because of

the innocent Eddie and partly because of his inability of fathering any child, Basil decides to make a difference in the lives of these fatherless boys. He takes them for outing every week and looks after them in absence of their mother. Keisha's seemingly careless behaviour towards her children surprises Basil very much when she allows him to take her sons to circus without knowing much about him and she "was only too happy to think that someone was going to take them off her hands for a day. It was alarming how easily she agreed. She and Helen weren't that close, what if I were a pervert she'd just handed her kids off to?" (*The Men of Brewster Place* 55).

Burdened with motherly duties as early as she enters the teenage, Keisha seems to be fed up with the tiresome job of looking after two children. She wishes to live like a free bird and enjoy her life fully, but finds herself chained with the unwanted responsibility of two children. She is too self-centred to pay any attention to the emotional void that her children feel. Keisha never kisses them good-bye and doesn't want to spend any money to take her kids out, but wastes a larger amount of time and money on herself to look attractive as she always remains "decked out in a dress too tight for her plump body and smelling like a perfume factory...it cost close to hundred dollars every month to keep her hair braided so neatly with those extensions..." (58). She prefers to enjoy her own life with her boyfriends rather than take care of her children.

Keisha doesn't like to be confined to the home space, fulfilling her motherly duties. When Basil offers to take the boys out, Keisha's unpredictable behaviour causes a lot of problems for Basil. As Basil tells: "Sometimes she promises I could take the boys out and when I show up at the apartment, she doesn't let them go. That starts the kids crying; the crying starts her to yelling; and we're all standing there in a mess" (57). Whenever Keisha wants to go out on weekends, she makes Basil to baby-sit her sons. She seems too careless to tell them anything

about her return and keeps them waiting for the whole night. As most of the times she doesn't come back, Basil has to take care of the children.

When Basil, out of his love for children, proposes Keisha for marriage, she, at first hesitates due to their age gap, but agrees soon finding that he is a man with solid bank balance, saying: "I'm doing this for my kids... they need a father and I think you'd be a good one" (59). Keisha is smart enough to take the benefit of Basil's love towards her children. She spends all his money lavishly on herself as she purchases a new Cadillac, new living-room furniture, clothes and gifts for her male friends. Even after her marriage to Basil, she continues spending nights out. Though Basil dominates in every matter related to the boys, he doesn't dare to interfere in her personal life. While Basil dreams big for the boys and keeps their morale high, Keisha thinks it useless even to build a college fund for the boys, saying: "Don't promise them too much,'... 'They'll grow up and be disappointed. I wanted to be a teacher and look at me'" (60).

Keisha, who is a high school dropout, also seems to be a case of a dream deferred. In a society that inflicts so much pain on the psyche of black woman in the form of intersecting oppressions of race, class, gender and sexuality, Keisha finds it too hard to realize her dream of becoming a teacher. Initiated in her sexual life in the early stage of life, she is forced to leave her dreams of a decent and dignified life. She keeps herself hanging on different men even after her conditional marriage to Basil. Everything goes on smoothly until Basil discovers that Keisha brings her men home in his absence. When he tries to control her waywardness, she becomes violent and tries to hit her son, Eddie. Basil, who is fully devoted to his sons, warns her to keep her hands off his kids. Basil's claim on the boys makes Keisha so furious that she hurls curses at him, saying:

“Your kids? They ain’t your kids. Since when you man enough to have any kids. You hardly ever touch me. They told me not to marry some old ass like you.” And then her eyes narrowed as she went for the jugular. “For all you know, Penny might be their real father. And even if he ain’t, he’s sure as hell better in bed than you are.” (*The Men of Brewster Place* 61)

The reaction from Keisha underscores the frustration of a young wife who is ignored by her husband in his desperation to prove himself an ideal father. Even Basil accepts his failure as a husband as he thinks: “May be some of this was my fault. May be if I’d concentrated on being as good a husband as I did a father, I could have saved the marriage” (60). Realising that Keisha’s waywardness is affecting their children, Basil tries to control her unbridled sexual autonomy by enacting physical violence. As a domineering woman, she pays him back in the same coin by bouncing back at him and tells him to get out of her life. When Basil claims his right on the kids, Keisha dismisses his claim thoroughly, saying: “Man, are you outta your mind? You ain’t taking my kids nowhere” (62). Margaret Early Whitt has rightly observed the root-cause behind this bitterness in marital relationship as she states: “In his ultimate marriage to Keisha, he learns that placing fatherhood *before* a meaningful and loving relationship with his children’s mother, who happens to be his wife, throws his pledge to make some woman happy off balance” (210).

The author also highlights the predicament of children due to the conflicting parental relationships as they find themselves sandwiched between the two. After one week of their embittered fight, Basil is detained by the detectives who carry an arrest warrant against him. All his efforts to make a difference in the lives of these boys are dashed to the ground when, after serving six years in jail, he finds the boys substantially ruined by their mother. Jason involves

himself in unlawful acts and Eddie cuts himself off the outer world by building a hard and permanent shell around him. In Basil's absence, Keisha remains busy enjoying life with Penny and gives a damn care to the needs of her children which makes them both "a lost generation" (Naylor, *The Men of Brewster Place* 57).

Eugene-Ceil relationship attracts much attention as the most loving couple in the novel. Eugene recalls Ceil (spelt "Ciel" in *The Women of Brewster Place*) as a tough girl who had won his heart right from the beginning. Though tall and skinny, she is very strong and, like a boy, can run fast. She loves running and her long, brown legs seem almost flying effortlessly because of her "lean, boyish body built for speed" (70). Since her childhood, Ceil has relished much attention due to her extraordinary personality. It is only because of her forceful presence that she is allowed to play stickball with the boys who want her desperately in their team to ensure their victory because she plays so brilliantly in the centre field "that nothing short of a home run got away" (70). Eugene eulogizes Ceil, saying: "'You're already special. You can run faster than any boy in town, except, maybe, Bug Eye. You can climb higher. And God knows, you've got a great pitching arm'" (71). He appreciates Ceil for her love for reading and writing. When he asks her to be his pen friend, she readily accepts, saying: "'I like to write letters'" (70).

Ceil is an ambitious girl who dreams big and wants to be special by doing something extraordinary, transcending the confines of intersecting oppressions of race, class, gender and sexuality. Her perpetual dream of exploring the world outside Tennessee by flying around it in a plane is clouded with doubts as she questions Eugene in one of her letters: "Can black girls be airplane pilots?" (*The Men of Brewster Place* 70). Her marriage to Eugene brings a drastic change in her life. She dreams to buy a red brick house with a large yard furnished with a swing set and sliding board for their daughter, Serena. Though Ceil and Eugene are a loving couple,

Ceil has to suffer a lot due to the uncertain behaviour of Eugene, who desperately tries to reconcile between his homosexual urges and his love for his wife. As an assertive wife, Ceil questions his abrupt departure: “Why did [he] keep leaving?” (70). During one of their heated arguments, they leave their daughter Serena unattended, who gets electrocuted and dies. This untoward incident leaves Ceil in a traumatized state. The irresponsible behaviour shown by Eugene during this crucial phase of their life puts an end to their marital life.

Annette, the late wife of Moreland T. Woods, had much influence on his life. He recalls her as an ambitious woman who always aspired for more: “A snippet of a woman but with appetite as large and ambitious as his. And it was finally on her advice that they became regular members of Sinai Baptist” (104). It was only because of Annette that Moreland was able to recognize his hitherto unrecognized aptitude for preaching and also “that he could be so comfortable up at the altar” (104). Annette was a perfect human being and a considerate wife who knew very well how to deal with the disloyalty of her husband. Even her silence was so forceful that it often made Woods guilty conscious as he remembers:

As long as he was discreet, she remained silent. And that silence was more effective than any arguments or screaming would have been. It weighed like a club that he used to beat up on himself, promising with all his heart that it would never happen again. And it never did—until it happened again. (109)

Abshu’s mother, an embodiment of love and sacrifice, is always ready to do anything for the betterment of her children. She is given a brutal treatment by her husband who is deprived of his right to feel like a man by the hegemonic white society. His frustration on account of the repeated failures and his pain of being silent in the face of oppressive treatment given to him for

being black turn him into a stone-hearted man. All his anger accumulated against the racist society is targeted upon his wife. As Collins states:

Failure to challenge an overall climate that not only defines Black masculinity in terms of Black men's ability to "own" and "control" their women, and Black femininity in terms of Black women's ability to help U.S. Black men feel like men, can foster African-American women's abuse. Black men who feel that they cannot be men unless they are in charge can be highly threatened by assertive Black women, especially those in their own households. (157)

Abshu's mother is in a complicated and troubled relationship with her husband, who always begs her pardon for mistreating her. Though a considerate and submissive wife, she is a courageous mother who decides to send all her children in foster care to save them from the physical violence enacted upon them by their father. It is only due to her sacrifice of motherly feelings that she is able to make at least one of her children worthy enough to live a decent and respectable life. The way Abshu's mother makes efforts to bring out the basic goodness in her son, introduces us with her innate powers as a black woman. Naylor through the character of Abshu's mother highlights the virtues of love and sacrifice as the bedrock of black motherhood.

Mother Mason, a tiny woman in her fifties, accepts Abshu in her house from foster care. She lives in a small wooden bungalow right on the edge of Linden Hills. Quite contrary to her husband who rarely speaks, Mother Mason twitters like a bird and uses baby talk to emphasize her words. As a strict disciplinarian, she never lets the boys eat prior to the fixed time. She is such a calculated mind that there are no leftovers after the first serving and asking for more "was to be met with suspicion from Mother Mason—"Shame. Shame. Are you trying to say we mistreat you here? Don't be a piggy-piggy'" (*The Men of Brewster Place* 139). Though a miser

woman, Mother Mason's disciplined and strict measures of living keep the boys away from street gangs. Even Abshu admits that it is only because of the "strict curfew" meant to be observed and the religious environment he finds in the house of Masons that he succeeds in creating a meaningful life for himself (140).

B.B. Rey's mother is a woman with strong determination and willpower who can go to any extent to make her children successful in their lives. Though she marries a Puerto Rican who works in the post office, she, just for love, likes to be called Colombian and shapes her children also in the same way. Rey's mother is a certified nut and represents a variety of cultures as she finds in her veins the mixed blood of "an American goulash with bits of Irish, a sprinkling of Scottish, a touch of German, and the whopping dose of French" (147). Instead of bragging about the white blood in her veins, she prefers to be called a black woman. Right from the beginning she puts in the mind of her son, Rey that he has to be a lawyer. She creates such an environment around her son that keeps him reminding of his ultimate aim in life:

So, unlike other infants, when B.B. first spoke it wasn't "ma-ma" or "da-da" or any of that stuff. His first words were "litigate, litigate" which he took to mean "I'm hungry, bring me a bottle." But he quickly moved to the next stage of yelling "habeas corpus" when he wanted to be picked up and held or "objection, objection" when he wanted to say no. (147)

Conclusion

Thus, by presenting a variety of man-woman relationships in her novel *The Men of Brewster Place*, Naylor recognizes the significance of complete harmony between husband and wife to provide a congenial environment for the growth and development of the whole family

especially the children. The children like Abshu and B.B.Ray succeed in creating a meaningful life for themselves just because they get a disciplined and favourable environment either in foster care or at home, while the children like Ben's daughter and Keisha's sons are doomed due to the unending fights between their parents. Most of the relationships are strained because of the frustration that arises among black people because of the dream deferred or denied. The existing definitions of true manhood and womanhood in the white hegemonic society also force black people to fit themselves into those moulds which are contrary to their living realities and also to the norms of their own black culture. The author also suggests that the failure of marriages in the black community is mainly because of the financial crisis faced by black people in a society that is plagued by the intersections of race, class, gender and sexuality. The author keeps the conviction that both husband and wife should be considerate enough to give space, liberty, emotional support and respect to each other for a redemptive marital relationship.

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